

Evaluation of Prescribing Pattern of Antibiotics in the Outpatient Department of Tertiary Care Hospital According to WHO Prescribing IndicatorsMohammed S¹, Kommareddy S², Vattam J³¹Clinical Trial Lead, AbbVie Inc.²Lab Manager, Advanced Health Informatics³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Geethanjali College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad.

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Abstract:

Background: Increasing antimicrobial resistance is a cause of concern in health care and needs to be addressed with immediate effect to prevent future consequences. Evaluation of prescribing patterns at regular intervals facilitates the identification of problems related to drug use, sensitizes physicians, and helps in formulating guidelines for the rational use of medicine.

Material and Methods: This prospective, cross-sectional study was conducted in a tertiary care hospital over a period of 6 months. The WHO indicators were used to evaluate the prescriptions.

Results: A total of 930 prescriptions were collected. The average number of drugs per encounter was 3.1. The percentage of antibiotics prescribed was 40.7%. 1% of prescriptions have an injectable antibiotic prescribed, and 99% of drugs were prescribed from the essential medical list. Only 12.1% of antibiotics were prescribed by their generic name.

Conclusion: the prescriptions deviate from the recommended values set by the WHO. Continuous education and training activities for physicians and the appointment of clinical pharmacists in the wards are recommended to improve the rational use of medicines.

Keywords: Rational Use, Who Indicators, Antimicrobial Resistance.

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Introduction

Antibiotics are the drugs used to prevent and treat infections caused by microorganisms. They can be bacteriostatic or bactericidal and act at different stages of the cell cycle that inhibit or prevent the growth of microbes. In India, they come under Schedule H, in the Drugs Act 1945 i.e. they should be used under the guidance of a registered medical practitioner. They are a part of the red line campaign initiated by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare to prevent the emergence of antibiotic resistance [1].

Antimicrobial resistance is when organisms are no longer susceptible to the given antimicrobial agent resulting in a lack of effectiveness and thereby the failure of treatment. This resistance is developed when an organism mutates or acquires foreign DNA, making it resistant to drugs. It is estimated that antimicrobial resistance (AMR) resulted in 1.27 million deaths in 2019 and is one of the top global health emergencies. In India, 297,000 deaths were due to AMR in 2019 and it is the 3rd leading cause of death that year [2]. In addition to death and disability, AMR is also associated with significant healthcare costs and economic burden on society [3].

WHO in association with the International Network of Rational Use of Drugs (INRUD) developed a set of indicators to assess rational drug use at a healthcare facility. Even though the recommendations are in place, more than half of the drugs are prescribed inappropriately and most of the patients take the medicines inappropriately [4]. Irrational drug use leads to adverse health outcomes and an increase in health economic burden. Concerning antibiotics, inappropriate use of these drugs leads to the development of AMR.

Evaluation of prescribing patterns at regular intervals facilitates the identification of problems related to drug use, sensitizing physicians and helps in formulating guidelines for rational use of medicine. The present study was conducted considering this in this hospital setting to promote rational drug use, using WHO prescribing indicators.

Materials and Methods

This is a prospective, cross-sectional study conducted in the outpatient department of a 1000-bed tertiary care hospital in Hyderabad from June 2023 to November 2023. The patients between the age

groups of 18-80 years, of both genders, who were willing to participate in the study were included.

The study was initiated after getting institutional ethical committee permission and informed consent was taken from the patient before collecting the data.

Data Collection

A carefully designed data collection form was used to collect data like demographic details, current illness, number and names of drugs prescribed, duration of treatment, number of drugs prescribed by generic name, route of administration, and duration of therapy. Consent was taken from the patients after receiving medicine in the pharmacy and data was collected.

WHO Indicators

The data obtained was analyzed using WHO prescribing indicators:

1. Average number of drugs per patient encounter.

2. Percentage of encounters with an antibiotic prescribed.
3. Number of encounters with an injection prescribed.
4. Percentage of antibiotics with a generic name.
5. Percentage of antibiotics prescribed from the essential medical list.

Data Analysis

All the data was entered into MS Excel data sheet and descriptive statistics were applied.

Results

930 prescriptions were collected after the patient received medicine from the pharmacy. The data was entered into Microsoft Excel. Description statistics were used.

Out of 930 patients, 520 were male and 410 were female patients. Half of the sample falls within the age group of 18-50 (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic data

Patient characteristics	Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	520	55.9%
Female	410	44.1%
Age		
<18 years	220	23.6%
18-50	450	48.4%
>50 years	260	28%

The most common illnesses identified were respiratory tract infections, ulcers, non-communicable diseases, GI disturbances, skin infections, and gynecological issues (table 2).

Table 2: Distribution of illness

S. No.	Type of illness	Percentage of illness
1	Respiratory tract infections	33
2	Gastrointestinal infections and disorders	22
3	Metabolic disorders	20
4	Gynecological disorders	10
5	Skin and soft tissue infections	6
6	Urinary tract infections	5
7	others	4

The average number of drugs prescribed was 3.1 and 40.7% of prescriptions contain an antibiotic (Table 3). The common drugs prescribed were antibiotics, analgesics and antipyretics, gastrointestinal drugs, cardiovascular drugs, vitamins and minerals, and antidiabetic medicine.

Table 3: distribution of drugs among the prescriptions

S. No.	Distribution of drugs	Percentage of encounters (%)
1	Antibiotics	40.7%
2	Antipyretics and analgesics	20.5%
3	Antiulcer agents	42.5%
4	Cardiovascular drugs	17%
5	Vitamins and minerals	35.6%
6	others	10.8%

The most prescribed antibiotics were amoxicillin, azithromycin, cefixime, ciprofloxacin, amoxicillin + clavulanic acid, and doxycycline (table 4).

Table 4: commonly prescribed antibiotics

S. No.	Antibiotics	Percentage (%)
1	Amoxicillin	29.3
2	Azithromycin	18
3	Cefixime	12
4	Ciprofloxacin	8
5	Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid	9
6	Metronidazole	5
7	Doxycycline	8.1
8	Others	10.6

Table 5 shows the comparison of our study values with that of the recommended values given by WHO.

Table 5: WHO prescribing indicators

Indicator	Value	Who Optimal Values
Average number of drugs per patient encounter	3.1	1.6-1.8
Percentage of encounters with an antibiotic-prescribed	40.7%	20% - 26.8%
Number of encounters with an injection prescribed	1%	13.4%- 24.1%
Percentage of antibiotics with a generic name	12.1%	100%
Percentage of antibiotics prescribed from Essential medical list	99%	100%

Discussion

The Number of encounters with an injection prescribed was 1% and is the only indicator which is below the WHO optimal value. Sample collection in the outpatient setting may explain the lower percentage of prescriptions with the injections. This is similar to the study conducted in South India where only 1.6% of prescriptions have injections prescribed [5].

The average number of drugs per patient encounter was found to be 3.1 which is slightly above the optimal value. Compared to a study conducted in Pune [6], the value is considerably low, where the average number of drugs prescribed was 6.12 per patient encounter. The reasons for Polypharmacy are multifaceted and may include Ambiguity in diagnosis, patient seeking quick relief, non-availability of essential medicine, or availability of irrational combinations or aggressive pharmaceutical promotion. Prescribing multiple drugs at a time leads to medication errors, drug interactions, adverse effects, an increase in economic burden, and failure of therapy. Hence, it should be discouraged.

The percentage of encounters with antibiotics prescribed is 40.7% which is above the standard value. It is less compared to two other studies conducted in India and Ethiopia where the values were 51.5% [7] and 82.5% [8], respectively. The excess use of antibiotics can be because of the high incidence of infectious diseases in these areas, and socio-economic and cultural backgrounds. The greater the prescribing of the antibiotics, the higher the chances for AMR.

The percentage of antibiotics with a generic name is 12.1% only, which is very low. Prescribing by generic name ranges from 2.5% [9] to 87.5% [10] in South India itself. These variabilities within the same geographical region may be because of faith in branded drugs, excess promotion by industries, and lack of strict rules to prescribe generic drugs. Prescribing by generic drugs decreases the cost of treatment, and dispensing errors, and increases co-ordination and understanding between prescribers and clients.

The percentage of antibiotics prescribed from the essential medical list was found to be 99% which is near to the optimal value. This is better than the prescription pattern observed in a study in central Kerala [11], where the value was found to be 69%. The drugs in the essential medical list are old, time-tested with proven efficacy, and less expensive. Prescribing from essential medical lists is one of the means of achieving rational drug use. It indicates that the drug management in this hospital is according to the national recommendations.

Conclusion

This study shows the prescribing pattern of antibiotics in the tertiary care hospital. The study shows deviation from the WHO prescribing indicators regarding the number of drugs prescribed, percentage of antibiotic use, and prescribing by generic name. However, the number of injections prescribed and drugs prescribed from the essential drug list is found to be optimum. It is recommended that continuous education and training activities for physicians regarding rational prescribing be conducted. Furthermore, we recommend the appointment of a clinical pharmacist in each ward to

oversee prescription patterns and provide valid suggestions whenever needed.

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